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Glycyrrhizin and COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

I hypothesized in March 2020 that glycyrrhizin from liquorice root might be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 because previous studies showed that glycyrrhizin has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses. Later on, several researchers confirmed that glycyrrhizin can be used as a therapeutic for COVID-19 and as a preventive agent against SARS-CoV-2.

INTRODUCTION

I hypothesized in March 2020 that glycyrrhizin from liquorice root might be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 because previous studies showed that glycyrrhizin has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses.

AN UPDATE

Luo and coworkers discussed in their article the therapeutic potential of glycyrrhizin for the treatment of COVID-19 from the perspective of its pharmacological action, including binding angiotensin-converting enzyme II (ACE2), downregulating proinflammatory cytokines, inhibiting the accumulation of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), inhibiting thrombin, inhibiting the hyperproduction of airway exudates, and inducing endogenous interferon, but the

biological function of glycyrrhizin is drawn from in vitro findings and animal experiments and may not correspond with clinical efficacy in humans. Authors concluded that the exact clinical curative effect and the optimal dose and course of treatment must be further assessed¹.

Bailly and Vergoten analyzed the anti-coronavirus potential of the natural product glycyrrhizic acid (GLR), a drug used to treat liver diseases (including viral hepatitis) and specific cutaneous inflammation (such as atopic dermatitis) in some countries. GLR has shown activities against different viruses, including SARS-associated Human and animal coronaviruses. GLR is a non-hemolytic saponin and a potent immuno-active anti-inflammatory agent which displays both cytoplasmic and membrane effects. At the membrane level, GLR induces cholesterol-dependent disorganization of lipid rafts

which are important for the entry of coronavirus into cells. At the intracellular and circulating levels, GLR can trap the high mobility group box 1 protein and thus blocks the alarmin functions of HMGB1. Authors used molecular docking to characterize further and discuss both the cholesterol- and HMG box-binding functions of GLR. The membrane and cytoplasmic effects of GLR, coupled with its long-established medical use as a relatively safe drug, make GLR a good candidate to be tested against the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, alone and in combination with other drugs. Authors concluded that GLR should be further considered and rapidly evaluated for the treatment of patients with COVID-19².

Chrzanowski and coworkers explained in their article that glycyrrhizin (GZ) is a promising agent against SARS-CoV-2 as its antiviral activity against SARS-CoV has already been confirmed. It is worthwhile to extrapolate from its proven therapeutic effects as there is a high similarity in the structure and genome of SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2. There are many possible mechanisms through which GZ acts against viruses: increasing nitrous oxide production in macrophages, affecting transcription factors and cellular signaling pathways, directly altering the viral lipid-bilayer membrane, and binding to the

ACE2 receptor. Authors discussed the possible use of GZ in the COVID-19 setting, where topical administration appears to be promising, with the nasal and oral cavity notably being the potent location in terms of viral load. The most recently published papers on the distribution of ACE2 in the human body and documented binding of GZ to this receptor, as well as its antiviral activity, suggest that GZ can be used as a therapeutic for COVID-19 and as a preventive agent against SARS-CoV-2³.

In a study (van de Sand and coworkers; December 20, 2020) researchers investigated aqueous licorice root extract for its neutralizing activity against SARS-CoV-2 *in vitro*, identified the active compound glycyrrhizin and uncovered the respective mechanism of viral neutralization. Authors demonstrated that glycyrrhizin, the primary active ingredient of the licorice root, potentially neutralizes SARS-CoV-2 by inhibiting the viral main protease, what highlights glycyrrhizin as a potential antiviral compound that should be further investigated for the treatment of COVID-19⁴.

Patel and coworkers concluded in their mini review that complementary and alternative medicine offers plenty of preventive and treatment options which can be implemented for masses in a short

period. Polyherbal formulations using medicinal herbs with a wide variety of properties like antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulating can be effectively deployed for management of current COVID-19 pandemic⁵.

Harald Murck concluded in his article that glycyrrhizin may reduce the severity of an infection with COVID-19 at two stages of the COVID-19 induced disease process: to block the number of entry points and provide an ACE2 independent anti-inflammatory mechanism⁶.

CONCLUSION

I hypothesized in March 2020 that glycyrrhizin from liquorice root might be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 because previous studies showed that glycyrrhizin has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses. Later on, several researchers confirmed that glycyrrhizin can be used as a therapeutic for COVID-19 and as a preventive agent against SARS-CoV-2.

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